

Table 1: Demographic data of respondents and their companies (1–8)

No.	Question
1	What is the position closest to your current role? (Single Choice) Developer; Data Analyst; QA; PO/PM; Tech Lead; DevOps; Others
2	What is your gender? (Single Choice) Female; Male; Non-binary; Prefer not to answer; Others
3	What is your age?
4	Approximately, how many years/months of experience do you have in the technology field?
5	Approximately, how long (years/months) have you worked at your current company?
6	What is your current work model? (Single Choice) On-site; Remote; Hybrid
7	What is the size of the company you currently work for? (Single Choice) Micro; Small; Medium; Large
8	What is the industry sector of the company you currently work for? (Single Choice) Finance; Marketing; Communication; Software; Commerce; Education; Agriculture; Investment; Others

Table 2: Data Privacy and Gen AI Trainings (9–11)

No	Question
9	During onboarding, does your company offer data privacy training? Mandatory; Optional; Does not exist; I don't know; I don't remember; There is no onboarding.
10	Does the company require periodic data privacy training? Regularly; Optional repetition; No requirement; Does not exist; I don't know; I don't remember; No onboarding.
11	Have you ever participated in training or received guidance on the use of generative AI in your company? Yes; No

Table 3: Using generative AI tools (12-17)

Nº	Pergunta
12	How often do you use generative AI tools at work? (Single Choice) Daily; Several times a week; Several times a month; Rarely; Never
13	Which generative AI tools do you use at work? (Multiple Choice) ChatGPT; Google Gemini; Microsoft Copilot; Github Copilot; Bard (Google); None; Others
14	What tasks do you perform using generative AI tools? (Multiple Choice) Coding; Code editing; Bug fixing; Code review; Test implementation; Test fixing; Writing and reviewing technical documentation; Business refinement; Issue commenting; Email writing; Planning; Others
15	Does your company have paid subscriptions for the generative AI tools you use? (Multiple Choice) Paid by company; Paid by me; Free; I don't use; Others
16	Agreement level: "My company authorizes the use of generative AI tools at work." Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree
17	Agreement level: "My company encourages the use of generative AI tools at work." Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree

Table 4: Use of personal and third-party data and risk perception (18-24)

No.	Question
18	Agreement level: "I use my own personal data in generative AI tools." Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree
19	Agreement level: "Using my company's information in generative AI tools poses a risk to my company." Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree
20	Can you explain your answer to the previous question?
21	Agreement level: "There are risks of information leakage from my company when using generative AI tools in my software development tasks." Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree
22	Can you explain your answer to the previous question?
23	Agreement level: "It is not necessary to apply any technique to mask sensitive data before submitting it to a generative AI tool." Strongly Agree; Agree; Neutral; Disagree; Strongly Disagree
24	Can you explain your answer to the previous question?